

Synthesis of Oxygenated Deoxybenzoins and Isoflavones

B. S. UMA RANI and MALLESHWAR DARBARWAR*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

Manuscript received 13 September 1985, revised 29 July 1987, accepted 11 August 1987

Eight new deoxybenzoins have been prepared by alkali cleavage of 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins and subsequently converted with ethyl formate to corresponding isoflavones. The structures of deoxybenzoins and isoflavones were established by spectral data and their useful physiological properties discussed.

A facile method for the synthesis of oxygenated 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins communicated earlier¹ involved condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarins with *p*-benzoquinone and conversion of the resulting intermediates 3-*p*-benzoquinonyl-4-hydroxycoumarins into 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins by Thiele's acetylation/reductive acetylation and subsequent hydrolysis. This method has now been extended for the synthesis of deoxybenzoins, which are formed as a result of alkali cleavage of 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins.

Isoflavones^{2,3} exhibit oestrogenic, insecticidal, piscicidal and antifungal properties. They are known to occur in forage legumes such as subterranean red clover, and have been recognised as cause of infertility problems occurring in animals grazing these species^{4,5}. The synthesis of naturally occurring isoflavones has been restricted because of inaccessibility of the starting materials, *viz.* deoxybenzoins. It was therefore considered worthwhile to convert the polyhydroxydeoxybenzoins into the corresponding isoflavones with a view to evaluating their physiological properties. The present communication deals with preparation, characterisation and study of physiological properties of some deoxybenzoins and isoflavones.

As a representative case, 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin and *p*-benzoquinone were condensed in acetone to give 3-*p*-benzoquinonyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin which on Thiele's acetylation and hydrolysis offered 4-hydroxy-6-methyl-3-(2',4',5'-trihydroxyphenyl)coumarin (1). In the present investigation, 1 was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide for 6 h. Alkaline hydrolysis and subsequent decarboxylation gave rise to a light brown compound, m.p. 193°, M^+ m/z 274, molecular formula $C_{15}H_{14}O_5$, single spot on tlc, silica gel G, ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 1), positive tests with ferric chloride and 2,4-DNP; λ_{max} 255 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.25, benzoyl chromophore); ν_{max} at 3400 (OH) and 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O). The ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) was not satisfactory because of

poor solubility of the compound. Therefore, its acetate (m.p. 159°) was prepared (Ac_2O/Py) and the ¹H nmr spectrum of the acetate (in DMSO- d_6) showed four signals at δ 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 (each 3H, s) assignable to acetate protons. Signals at δ 2.7 (3H, s, methyl), 4.8 (2H, s, methylene) and 7.2-7.5 (5H, m, aromatic) were also present. On the basis of the above chemical and spectral data, the parent compound has been characterised as 5-methyl-2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxydeoxybenzoin (2, Chart 1).

Chart 1.

The molecular ion peak at m/z 274 with 100% intensity indicated the deoxybenzoin a stable molecule. Its fragmentation pathways have been delineated in Chart 2.

The deoxybenzoin (2), ethyl formate and sodium metal were stirred for 6 h at 0°. A light yellow compound was formed, m.p. 278°, M^+ m/z 234, molecular formula $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$, tlc single spot on silica gel G, ethyl acetate; λ_{max} 265 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.35, benzoyl chromophore) and 315 (4.00); ν_{max} 3390 (OH) and 1660 cm^{-1} (C=O). This compound was also converted into the colourless acetate (Ac_2O/Py) and the ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) showed three signals at δ 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 (each 3H, s) for

acetate protons. Methyl protons were present at δ 2.7 (3H, s) and aromatic protons at δ 7.1–7.5

(5H, m). A signal at δ 7.8 (1H, s) has been assigned for H-2, characteristic of isoflavone, thus confirming the presence of isoflavone structure. On the basis of above spectral data, the compound has been assigned 6-methyl-2',4',5'-trihydroxyisoflavone structure (3, Chart 3).

The molecular ion of the parent isoflavone (m/z 284) indicated characteristic loss of one hydrogen radical to form an ion at m/z 283 which constituted the base peak in the mass spectrum. Further, M^+ underwent RDA process to form the ions at m/z 134 and 150. The former ion lost CO to give ion at m/z 106. Chart 4 presents the possible structures of these ions.

Following the above procedure, 2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxydeoxybenzoin, 5-chloro-2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxybenzoin and 5-chloro-4-methyl-2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxydeoxybenzoin were prepared by alkaline cleavage of respective 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins. The yields were good in all the cases. There-

fore, it constitutes a good method for the preparation of deoxybenzoins. These were cyclised with ethyl formate to isoflavones, namely 2',4',5'-trihydroxyisoflavone, 6-chloro-2',4',5'-trihydroxyisoflavone and 6-chloro-7-methyl-2',4',5'-trihydroxyisoflavone.

In addition to the above tetrahydroxybenzoins, four trihydroxydeoxybenzoins were prepared in the following manner. As a typical case, 3-(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl)-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (4) was prepared by reductive acetylation of 3-*p*-benzoquinonyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin using $Ac_2O/Py/Zn$ followed by hydrolysis. The compound 4 offered 5-methyl-2,2',5'-trihydroxydeoxybenzoin (5) by alkali cleavage, m.p. 223°, tlc single spot; λ_{max} 258 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.24, benzoyl chromophore); ν_{max} 3300 (OH) and 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O). The above deoxybenzoin was converted by ethyl formate/sodium into 2',5'-dihydroxy-6-methylisoflavone (6; Chart 5), m.p. 214°, tlc single spot on silica gel G, ethyl acetate; λ_{max} 268 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.37, benzoyl chromophore) and 315 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.10); ν_{max} 3390 (OH) and 1660 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Other deoxybenzoins prepared by the above method are 2,2',5'-trihydroxydeoxybenzoin, 5-chloro-2,2',5'-trihydroxydeoxybenzoin, 5-chloro-4-methyl-2,2',5'-trihydroxydeoxybenzoin, and these were

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF DEOXYBENZOINS (2)

Sl. no.	R ¹	R ²	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula*	λ_{max}^{OH} (log ϵ) nm	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	
							OH	C=O
1.	OH	5-Methyl	193	67	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₅	255 (4.25)	3 400	1 680
2.	OH	H	185	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₅	258 (4.25)	3 400	1 680
3.	OH	5-Chloro	189	72	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₅ Cl	260 (4.30)	3 350	1 690
4.	OH	5-Chloro-4-methyl	201	78	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₅ Cl	253 (4.29)	3 300	1 690
5.	H	5-Methyl	223	79	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄	258 (4.24)	3 300	1 680
6.	H	H	213	62	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄	260 (4.30)	3 400	1 680
7.	H	5-Chloro	219	73	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ Cl	261 (4.29)	3 350	1 690
8.	H	5-Chloro-4-methyl	222	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl	265 (4.20)	3 300	1 680

*Satisfactory C and H analyses were obtained.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE ISOFLAVONES (3)

Sl. no.	R ¹	R ²	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula*	λ_{max}^{OH} (log ϵ) nm	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	
							OH	C=O
1.	OH	6-Methyl	278	59	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₅	265 (4.35)	3 390	1 660
2.	OH	H	285	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	315 (4.0)	3 390	1 650
3.	OH	6-Chloro	281	74	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₅ Cl	265 (4.35)	3 350	1 665
4.	OH	6-Chloro-7-methyl	290	67	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₅ Cl	315 (4.13)	3 350	1 660
5.	H	6-Methyl	284	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄	270 (4.32)	3 390	1 660
6.	H	H	273	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	310 (3.98)	3 380	1 660
7.	H	6-Chloro	279	68	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₄ Cl	272 (4.31)	3 350	1 650
8.	H	6-Chloro-7-methyl	286	77	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ Cl	312 (4.0)	3 400	1 660
						268 (4.37)		
						315 (4.10)		
						270 (4.38)		
						320 (4.05)		
						265 (4.25)		
						325 (4.0)		
						272 (4.32)		
						330 (4.0)		

*Satisfactory C and H analyses were obtained.

converted¹¹ later into 2',5'-dihydroxyisoflavone, 6-chloro-2',5'-dihydroxyisoflavone and 6-chloro-2',5'-dihydroxy-7-methylisoflavone, respectively by ethyl formate in presence of sodium. All the deoxybenzoins and isoflavones gave satisfactory analytical and spectral data, presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Physiological activity: The deoxybenzoins and isoflavones prepared were tested for their antibacterial (tube-dilution method) and antifungal (plate method) activities. All the compounds were found active. The most active among the compounds

tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* were 5-chloro-2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxydeoxybenzoin, 5-chloro-4-methyl-2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxydeoxybenzoin, 6-chloro-2',4',5'-trihydroxyisoflavone, 6-chloro-7-methyl-2',4',5'-trihydroxyisoflavone, 6-chloro-2',4',5'-triacetoxyisoflavone and 6-chloro-7-methyl-2',4',5'-triacetoxyisoflavone at 10 ppm. The most active among the compounds tested for antifungal activity against *A. niger* were 5-chloro-2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxydeoxybenzoin (70% inhibition), 5-chloro-4-methyl-2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxydeoxybenzoin (75% inhibition), 5-chloro-4-methyl-2,2',5'-trihydroxybenzoin (69% inhibition), 6-chloro-7-methyl-2',4',5'-tri-

acetoxylsoflavone (73% inhibition), 6-chloro-7-methyl-2',4',5'-trihydroxyisoflavone (72% inhibition), 6-chloro-2',5'-diacetoxylsoflavone (73% inhibition), 6-chloro-2',5'-dihydroxyisoflavone (72% inhibition) at 100 ppm.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structures were supported by elemental analysis (C, H), tlc, uv (MeOH) and ir (KBr).

General procedure :

5-Methyl-2,2',4',5'-tetrahydroxydeoxybenzoin (2) : 4-Hydroxy-6-methyl-3-(2',4',5'-trihydroxyphenyl) coumarin (**1**; 1.5 g) was dissolved in alcoholic methanolic 2% KOH (20 ml). The contents were refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h when **2** separated as a light brown solid which was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 193°.

6-Methyl-2',4',5'-trihydroxyisoflavone (3) : The deoxybenzoin (**2**; 1.37 g) was added to a mixture of ethyl formate (0.37 g) and sodium (0.12 g). The contents were stirred for 6 h at 0°, and then kept in a ice-chest overnight. The unreacted sodium was later destroyed by adding excess methanol. The light yellow coloured solid obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 278°.

References

1. B. S. UMA RANI and M. DARBARWAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 38.
2. W. B. WHALLEY in "Pharmacology of Plant Phenolics", ed. J. W. F. BAIR, Academic, London, 1959, p. 27.
3. J. D. BIGGERS in "Pharmacology of Plant Phenolics", ed. J. W. FAIRBAIRN, Academic, London, p. 51.
4. E. M. BICKOFF, Rev Ser. 1, Commonwealth Bureau of Pastures and Field Crops, Hurby, England, 1968, p. 1.
5. A. H. BRADEN and I. W. McDONALD, "Australian Grass Lands", Australian National University Press, Canberra, 1970, p. 38.